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Twin primes conjectures: some findings and correlations in the wake of a probabilistic approach

Abstract

Prime numbers have always fascinated mathematicians: Euclid's theorem which is a milestone in Number Theory, asserts that there are infinitely many prime numbers, while as regards primes of the form $p, p + 2$ (twin primes), despite all the efforts, this is still an unsolved conjecture. With an empirical approach, this paper compares experimental data to the expected values from a statistical and probabilistic perspective, with the aim to present some insights on the structure of prime pairs in the wake of the Dirichlet's theorem about arithmetic progressions, and on the correlation between first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture, Brun's Theorem and Legendre's conjecture, aiming to display a subtle *fil rouge* between celebrated conjectures and theorems.

Key words: *Dirichlet's theorem, 1st Hardy-Littlewood conjecture, Brun's theorem, Legendre's conjecture, Bertrand's postulate*

Introduction:

The twin prime conjecture which states that there are infinitely many primes of the form $p, p + 2$ is one of the best-known problems in Number Theory but despite the efforts and recent advancements (see [15]), it remains still unsolved and this is only one of the open problems that concern twin primes (see [3] and [9]).

In order to explore connections between isolated gems of Number theory and their possible extensions to twin primes, the study has been divided into six sections. In the first one it has been investigated the prime pair structure so as to verify if it exists a pattern similar to what is stated by Dirichlet's theorem about arithmetic progressions.

In the second one it has been investigated the Hardy-Littlewood conjecture error term, so as to describe the twin primes counting function and not only the asymptotic value. In the third one it has been provided the analytical link between the Hardy-Littlewood conjecture and Brun's theorem about the convergence of the reciprocals of twin primes.

In the fourth, the extension to twin primes of the famous Legendre's conjecture about prime numbers is justified starting from the Hardy-Littlewood conjecture, with some interesting consequences (Bertrand's postulate and Andrica's conjecture).

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All of this is carried out with a mixed method which combines the current tools of pure and applied mathematics, providing a little bigger *fresco* of what we know or suppose about twin primes (Table 1).

List of Conjectures	Prime Numbers	Twin Primes	Ref.
1. Distribution of Primes vs Twin Primes	$\pi(x; q, a) = \frac{\text{Li}(x)}{\phi(q)} + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}\right)$ $\forall \epsilon > 0$ <p>(with RH, i.e., Riemann Hypothesis)</p>	$\pi_z^k(x; q, a_k) \sim \frac{\pi_z(x)}{\omega(q)},$ $\pi_z^k(x; q, b_s) \sim \frac{\pi_z(x)}{\omega(q)},$ <p>and $\pi_z^k(x; q, (a_k, a_{kj})) \neq \frac{\pi_z(x)}{\omega(q)}$. (probabilistic approach)</p>	1.1, 1.2
2. Counting Function: $\pi(n)$ vs $\pi_2(n)$	$\pi(n) = \text{Li}(x) + O(\sqrt{x} \ln(x))$ <p>(with RH)</p>	$\pi_2(n) = 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{(\ln(x))^2} + O\left(\frac{\sqrt{n}}{(\ln(n))^\beta}\right),$ $\beta \in [3 \div 4]$ <p>(statistical validation)</p>	2
3. Legendre's Conjecture	$\exists p_j : n^2 \leq p_j \leq (n+1)^2, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$	$\exists (p_j, p_j + 2) : n^3 \leq p_j, p_j + 2 \leq (n+1)^3,$ $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$ <p>(with HLC, i.e., Hardy-Littlewood Conjecture, and numerical validation up to 10^{12})</p>	4.
Bertrand's Postulate	$\forall m \in \mathbb{N}, m \geq 2, \exists p_j : m \leq p_j \leq 2m.$	$\forall m \in \mathbb{N}, m \geq 2, \exists (p_j, p_j + 2) :$ $m^2 \leq p_j, p_j + 2 \leq 2m^2$ <p>(from Legendre's conjecture)</p>	5.
Andrica's Conjecture	$\sqrt[p_{j+1}]{} - \sqrt[p_j]{} < 1, \quad \forall n \geq 2.$	<p>Let $m_j = (p_j + p_{j+1})/2$, then</p> $\sqrt[m_{j+1}]{} - \sqrt[m_j]{} < 1, \quad \forall n \geq 3$	6.

Table 1: Twin Prime Conjectures and Findings at a Glance

Table 2 presents methods and tools used in the study of the Hardy-Littlewood conjecture⁴ error term, in the extension of the Dirichlet’s theorem to twin primes, and in the investigation of the subtle thread that links HLC to Brun’s Theorem and to Legendre’s conjecture.

Topic	Method	Tools	Software CPU	Sample size
Primes pairs structure	Statistic approach	χ^2 test	C++ / Math Quad-core /i7	$n = 10^8 \alpha = 0.05$
HLC Error term	Statistic approach	Q-Q / KPSS / ITA / FoD / SPt / PEt	C++ / Math Quad-core /i7	$n = 10^{11} \alpha = 0.05$
HLC and BTh correlation	Analytical approach			
HLC and LCj correlation	Analytical / Numerical	Numerical verification	C++ / Math Quad-core /i7	$n = 10^{11}$

Table 2: Summary of methods and computational tools. (for the abbreviation list, see Annex # 1)

1. Prime pairs pseudorandomness and Dirichlet’s theorem

Primes are pseudorandom since they seem like a random collection of natural numbers even if applying statistical mechanic some type of ‘deterministic randomness’ [11] can be found. Interestingly, it can be observed that Riemann hypothesis (RH) predicts a formula for p_n with an error $\mathcal{O}\sqrt{n \cdot \ln^3(n)}$ which is essentially the same type one would have expected if the primes were distributed according to the law of large numbers, *i.e.* as if it was a random process [11].

At the same time the distribution of primes shows some kind of regularity: Dirichlet’s theorem (1837) about arithmetic progressions states that the sequence of primes are evenly distributed among the reduced residue classes (*mod* q) and if the generalized Riemann hypothesis (GRH) holds, this leads to: $\pi(x; q, a) = \frac{\text{Li}(x)}{\varphi(q)} + \mathcal{O}\left(x^{\frac{1}{2} + \epsilon}\right)$ for every $\epsilon > 0$.

Something similar happens with prime pairs of the form $(p_i, p_i + z)$ (e.g. $z = 2$ twin primes, $z = 4$ cousin primes) : a study was conducted by Bortolamasi,

⁴hereinafter HLC

Tapia and Agama with reference to twin primes, cousin primes and sexy primes (here a brief summary; see [2] for more details). Numerical analysis compared experimental data to the expected values, from a statistic point of view, in the wake of an extension of Dirichlet's theorem.

Let:

$P_z = \{(p_i, p_i + z)\}$ set of prime pairs

$\varphi(q)$ = the Euler totient function

R = least positive reduced residue system (mod q)

$A = \{a_k\}$ $k = 1, 2, \dots, \omega 1(q)$ and $B = \{b_s\}$ $s = 1, 2, \dots, \omega 2(q)$ subsets of R

$X_k(z, q, a_k) = \{(p_i, p_i + z) \in P_z : a_k = p_i \text{ mod}(q)\}$ set of pairs of consecutive primes with gap z

(example: $X_1(2,10, 1)$, $X_2(2,10, 7)$, $X_3(2,10, 9)$)

$Y_s(z, q, b_s) = \{(p_i, p_i + z) \in P_z : b_s = (p_i + z) \text{ mod}(q)\}$

$\pi_z^k(x; q, a_k)$ the counting function of class $X_k(z, q, a_k)$

(example: $\pi_2^1(x; 10, 1)$, $\pi_2^2(x; 10, 7)$, $\pi_2^3(x; 10, 9)$)

$\pi_z^s(x; q, b_s)$ the counting function of class $Y_k(z, q, b_s)$

1.1 Distribution of prime pairs mod(q)

The critical point is to determine an adequate sample size which can estimate results for the whole population without formulation of *a priori* hypothesis about the distribution of the classes $X_k(z, q, a_k)$ and $Y_k(z, q, b_s)$. Sample size, test power, the effect size (ES) and significance level α are strictly correlated: as the sample size increases the test power P also increases: commonly used ES in chi-square test are the phi coefficient φ , the Cramer's V and Cohen's w that was used in this study.

If we assume the standard $w=0.2$ a very small sample x_0 will be obtained [2], but this sample size doesn't prove to be always satisfactory. Only with a larger sample size $x_0 = 10^8$ the test statistic⁵ provides an acceptable Test Power $P > 80\%$, therefore the study has been carried out with this value.

	Class# 1	Class# 2	Class# 3	χ^2
<i>twin primes</i>	146841	146953	146517	0.698
<i>cousin primes</i>	146720	146945	146594	0.431

⁵There are some existing commonly used goodness-of-fit tests (*e.g.* the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Kolmogorov, 1933; Smirnov, 1939) the Cramer - Von Mises test (Cramer&Von Mises 1928), etc.).The Chi-square test (also known as Pearson's Chi-square test) is a goodness-of-fit test and is widely used in many cases.

	<i>Class# 1</i>	<i>Class# 2</i>	<i>Class# 3</i>	χ^2
<i>sexy primes</i>	293573	293080	293255	0.426

Table 3: Example: sample $x_0 = 10^8$, $a_k = p_i \bmod(10)$

The χ^2 value is less than the critical value with two degrees of freedom ($\chi_{\text{crit}}^2 = 5.99$) in all cases. Hence the Chi-square statistical analysis performed up to $x_0=10^8$ with all tested values of $\text{mod}(q)$ supports the conjecture that prime pairs of the form $(p_i, p_i + z)$ thin out in classes $X_k(z, q, a_k)$ and $Y_s(z, q, b_s)$ with the same cardinality:

$$H_0 : \pi_z^k(x; q, a_k) \sim \frac{\pi_z(x)}{\omega(q)} \quad (1)$$

And symmetrically:

$$\pi_z^k(x; q, b_s) \sim \frac{\pi_z(x)}{\omega(q)} \quad (2)$$

This result corresponds to a standard probability (Test power $P > 80\%$) at significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

1.2 Patterns of residues (*mod q*) among strings of consecutive pairs of primes

Let $(p_i, p_i + z)$ and $(p_{i+1}, p_{i+1} + z)$ a pair of consecutive pairs of primes, $a_k = p_i \bmod(q)$ and $a_{kj} = p_{i+1} \bmod(q)$ such that $a_k, a_{kj} \in A$.

We have explored the number of occurrences of the pattern (a_k, a_{kj}) among consecutive pairs of primes of the form $(p_i, p_i + z)$.

a_1	a_{1j}	$\pi_2(x_0; 10, (1, a_{1j}))$	a_2	a_{2j}	$\pi_2(x_0; 10, (7, a_{2j}))$	a_3	a_{3j}	$\pi_2(x_0; 10, (9, a_{3j}))$
1	7	53091	7	9	53048	9	1	52762
	9	48498		1	48825		7	48789
	1	45235		7	45071		9	44960
χ^2	637			650			623	

Table 4: Example: Twin primes $\text{mod}(10)$ $x_0 = 10^8$

In this case the χ^2 value is much larger than the critical value with two degrees of freedom ($\chi_{\text{crit}}^2 = 5.99$). The Chi-square statistical analysis performed up to $x_0=10^8$ with all tested values of $\text{mod}(q)$ supports the conjecture that the equidistribution doesn't hold in the pairs of consecutive prime pairs, similarly to what happens in the pairs of consecutive primes: in this case the statistical

analysis leads to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), at significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and with a test power $P > 80\%$:

$$\pi_z^k(x; q, (a_k, a_{kj})) \neq \frac{\pi_z(x)}{\omega(q)} \quad (3)$$

1.3 Results of Section One

The main result of this section is that the empirical analysis supports the conjecture about the extension of Dirichlet's theorem to prime pairs at the standard probability and significance level (Test power $P > 80\%$, $\alpha = 0.05$). A kind of bias in the prime pairs sequence appears: they thin out in reduced residue classes (mod q) with the same cardinality. On the contrary the way the classes are filled in, is basically random (or still unknown): there is statistical significance in the unpredictability of the patterns of residues (mod q) among strings of consecutive prime pairs.

2. Hardy-Littlewood conjecture error term

The following are definitions and conventions to be used for the rest of this work.

Let:

$P = \{p_i\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$ set of primes.

$\pi_2(n)$ twin primes counting function.

$\pi_2(n) \sim 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{(\ln \ln(x))^2}$ (Hardy-Littlewood conjecture).

$C_2 = \prod_{p>2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p-1)^2}\right) = 0.6601618 \dots$ (twin primes constant, see [7]).

$\overline{\pi_2(n)} = 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{(\ln \ln(x))^2}$ estimation of $\pi_2(n)$ in the set $[2, +\infty)$ becoming more precise as n increases

At the state of the art the so called 'strong twin prime conjecture' (see [12]) which is a special case of the more general k -tuple conjecture, is still the best numerical approximation of the twin prime counting function $\pi_2(n)$.

Table 5 summarize the results about the HLC error trend.

n	$\pi_2(n)$	$\overline{\pi_2(n)}$	$ \pi_2(n) - \overline{\pi_2(n)} $	$\frac{ \pi_2(n) - \overline{\pi_2(n)} }{\pi_2(n)}$
10	2	4.8362	2.84	1.4180942
1E+02	8	13.535	5.54	0.6919359
1E+03	35	45.796	10.80	0.3084429
1E+04	205	214.211	9.21	0.0449314
1E+05	1224	1248.709	24.71	0.0201869
1E+06	8169	8248.030	79.03	0.0096743
1E+07	58980	58753.816	226.18	0.0038349
1E+08	440312	440367.794	55.79	0.0001267
1E+09	3424506	3425308.156	802.16	0.0002342
1E+10	27412679	27411416.532	1262.47	4.605E-05
1E+11	224376048	224368864.681	7183.32	3.201E-05
1E+12	1,871E+09	1870559866.819	25353.18	1.355E-05
1E+13	1,583E+10	15834598305.062	66566.94	4.204E-06
1E+14	1,358E+11	135780264894.490	56770.51	4.181E-07

Table 5: HLC error trend

2.1 The choice of the class of functions

If we look at the asymptotic expansion of the function: $2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} = 2C_2 \times (-li(2) + \frac{2}{\ln(2)} + \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)} + \frac{2n}{\ln^3(n)} + \frac{6n}{\ln^4(n)} + \dots)$ it is possible to deduce that the error term must be of an order lower than $\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}$. The power interpolation of $|\pi_2(n) - \overline{\pi_2(n)}|$ with steps 10^k $k = [6, 18]$, suggests an exponent β a little lower than 0.5 with a promising coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.97$. For this reason, in a heuristic approach, the function $\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)}$ ($\beta \geq 0$) has picked out to check if it can describe the HLC error term. It is worth noting that in everything concerned to primes and prime pairs these terms: n^α and $\ln^\beta(n)$ constantly recur⁶.

⁶Concerning twin primes, it is interesting to observe that the difference $\pi_2(n) - 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}$ changes sign many times: M.Wolf[13] checked numbers up to 2^{48} and from this data he conjectured that the number of sign changes $\nu(n)$ tends asymptotically to $\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln(n)}$

2.2 Test architecture

If we look at the numerical figures of $\pi_2(n)$ and $2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}$ we observe that with $n_0 = 10^{10}$ the ratio $\frac{2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}}{\pi_2(n)}$ is already very close to unity and the ratio $\frac{f(n)}{\pi_2(n)}$ very close to zero, hence it seems quite natural to perform the numerical analysis in the range $(10^6, 10^{11})$.

Let:

$$f(n) = \left| \pi_2(n) - 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} \right| \text{ HLC error term}$$

$$g(n) = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)} \quad (\beta \geq 0) \text{ class of functions describing HLC error term}$$

$$h(n) := \frac{f(n)}{g(n)} \text{ ratio between HLC error term and the target function } g(n)$$

2.2.1 Normal distribution

We know that some kind of random variables have a normal distribution: let $\mu(h(n))$ the mean value of $h(n)$, in this case we would have 95% of probability that the mean value of $h(n)$ lies within $\pm 2\sigma$ (standard deviation) and hence a high probability that it doesn't tend to infinity *i.e.* $f(n) = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)}\right)$.

Several tests have been performed to verify this hypothesis.

Figure 1: Diagram n.1: Q-Q plot $[10^6, 10^{11}]$ with $h(n)$ $\beta = 1$. The red line corresponds to the theoretical normal distribution

The Diagram (Fig.1) shows a positive skewed distribution (skewness ≈ 0.9). Similar results can be obtained with $\beta = 2$ and $\beta = 3$. Hence we can deduce

that the function $h(n)$ with $\beta = 1,2,3$ cannot be properly approximated with a normal distribution, at the same time it is not completely different and this is an interesting findings which can be useful for some statistic tests (e.g. t-Test).

2.2.2 Stationary signal test

It was explored a class of functions $h(n) = \frac{f(n)}{g(n)}$ in order to find something ‘similar’ to a weak stationary signal (WSS), namely a random process with 1st moment which do not vary with respect to n , with finite second moments and with covariance function depending only on the difference between n_1 and n_2 .

KPSS Trend analysis⁷ has been performed to check if $h(n)$ is stationary around a mean or linear trend (Fig.2).

Figure 2: Diagram n.2: KPSS Cumulative residuals vs # of observations (20,000).

KPSS test statistic has been proved to be much higher⁸ than the critical value (0.463 at 95% of probability). For this reason no other test has been performed and we can reject the hypothesis of a weak stationary signal, which is indeed a very strong conjecture that can be fairly rejected.

2.2.3 Correlation analysis

If we carefully look at the big O notation⁹ we observe that the trend stationary is not actually required: the key point is not to have neither an increasing not a decreasing trend of the function $h(n)$. Some tests have been performed, starting with the ‘Innovative Trend Analysis’¹⁰ (ITA).

Even if recent studies (F.Serinaldi et Al., 2020 [10]) call into question some aspects of the method, there is no doubt that it provides a first indication of the correlation.

From the following diagrams (Figs. 3 and 4) we can suspect that $h(n)$ with $\beta = 1$ will have a decreasing trend, while with $\beta = 3$ the trend seems more undefined.

⁷Kwiatkowski–Phillips–Schmidt–Shin (KPSS) tests

⁸More than 2 orders of magnitude (big spikes in the cumulative residuals are already a signal of non-stationarity)

⁹ $f(x) = \mathcal{O}(g(x))$ if exists a positive real number M such that $|f(x)| \leq M g(x)$ for all $x \geq x_0$

¹⁰One of the most common analyses performed in hydro-climate research

In order to provide a more clear answer, the correlation test has been applied to evaluate the association between $h(n)$ and n depending on exponent β

Figure 3: Diagram n.3: ITA with $\beta = 1$ (1:1 no trend line)

Figure 4: Diagram n.4 ITA with $\beta = 3$. 1:1 no trend line with limiting bandwidth (dashed lines)

What we are looking for is a kind of scattered diagram with no correlation between n and $h(n)$ (Fig.5). A quite strong¹¹ correlation (e.g. Pearson correlation coefficient $r=0.6$) is an indicator of a positive trend of the function $h(n) = \frac{f(n)}{g(n)}$ and it doesn't comply with the hypothesis that the error term: $f(n) = \left| \pi_2(n) - 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} \right|$ is $\mathcal{O}(g(n))$. For example $f(n)$ doesn't seem $\mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)}\right)$

¹¹A 'weak' or 'strong' correlation index depends on the context and on field of application. In this case considering no literature available and the high number of elements, $r=0.2-0.3$ has been considered a weak correlation

with $\beta = 30$. We can notice that with $\beta = 2 \div 4$ the coefficient r is close to zero ($r \approx 0$) while with lower values a decreasing trend becomes increasingly possible. On the contrary with values $\beta \gg 3$ a positive trend becomes quite evident. The Spearman test¹² (a nonparametric measure of rank correlation) provides similar values (e.g. with $\beta = 1$ $\rho = -0.178$ vs $r = -0.137$). The First order difference analysis (Fig.6), indicates a similar conclusion:

Figure 5: Diagram n.5: Pearson correlation coefficient r vs exponent β

Figure 6: Diagram n.6 first order differences mean vs exponent β

When a variable has no trend, the first differences have a mean equal to zero: in this case we can see that this happens with β in the range [1-4].

¹²It describes how well the relationship between two variables can be described using a monotonic function. \mathbf{H}_0 (Spearman correlation coefficient) : $\rho = \mathbf{0}$

2.3 Statistical significance

In order to verify the statistical significance a critical point is the number of samples in the range $[10^6 \div 10^{11}]$. There is no real difference in the correlation coefficient with already 2000 samples: the difference with 20000 and with 500,000 points is less than 1%. For this reason, since $\rho < \rho_c(2000)$ with $\beta=4$ we cannot reject the hypothesis there is no monotonic correlation at the critical significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

2.4 Results of section two and open problems

Statistic methods have been used to make an analysis and interpretation of the collected data to draw indications about the error term $f(n)$. Even if no definitive answer has been provided, in light of this analysis we can conjecture that the error term $f(n)$ can be described with a function of the type: $\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)}$ *i.e.*

$$\pi_2(n) = 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)}\right) \quad (4)$$

with the exponent β likely in the range $[3 \div 4]$.

At the same time we could use the big-omega notation to define the lower bound: in this case we can conjecture:

$$\pi_2(n) = 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} + \Omega\left(\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\ln^\beta(n)}\right) \quad (5)$$

with the exponent β in the range $[0 \div 1]$.

3. From Hardy-Littlewood conjecture to Brun's theorem

In 1921 V. Brun [4] proved that the sum of the reciprocals of twin primes converges. Even if this does not answer the question about their number, it shows the relative scarcity of twin primes within primes.

This paragraph points out that Hardy-Littlewood conjecture [6], which states an asymptotic equivalence between $\pi_2(n)$ and the logarithmic integral $2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}$ is strictly linked to Brun's theorem (the significance of this bridge, suggest us to present the proof as exposed in [1]).

Theorem:

If $\pi_2(n) \sim 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}$ then $\sum_{p,p+2 \text{ primes}} \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p+2} < +\infty$

Part 1: $\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}$ is upper bounded by $C \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}$ with $C > 1$

It is easy to observe (Hôpital's rule) that: $\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} \sim \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}$ at the same time we know that any convergent sequence is bounded, hence let $\{a_n\} = \frac{\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}}$, for

every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ it exists a real number $C > 1$ such that:

$$1 < \frac{\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}} \leq C \quad (6)$$

It may be interesting to provide an estimation¹³ of C in the set $[n_0, +\infty)$.

We proceed as follows:

$$\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} = \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln(x)} - \frac{x}{\ln(x)} \Big|_2^n = li(n) - li(2) - \frac{n}{\ln(n)} + \frac{2}{\ln(2)} \quad (7)$$

with $li(n) = \int_0^n \frac{dx}{\ln(x)}$

The asymptotic expansion (Poincaré expansion) of $li(n)$ for $n \rightarrow +\infty$ gives:

$$li(n) \sim \frac{n}{\ln(n)} \sum_0^\infty \frac{k!}{\ln^k(n)} \text{ i.e. } li(n) \sim \frac{n}{\ln(n)} + \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)} + \frac{2n}{\ln^3(n)}$$

Hence: $\overline{\pi_2(n)} = 2C_2 \cdot (-li(2) + \frac{2}{\ln(2)} + \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)} + \frac{2n}{\ln^3(n)} + \frac{6n}{\ln^4(n)} + \dots)$ where $li(2) = 1.045163\dots$ (see [8]).

The series is not convergent and an approximation¹⁴ is reasonable where the series is truncated at a finite number of terms with an error roughly of the same size as the next term. We observe that we have decreasing values of $C(n_0)$ as n_0 increases: for example let $n_0 = e^{24}$ in the set $[n_0, +\infty)$ $\frac{1}{\ln^2(n)} \geq \frac{24}{\ln^3(n)}$. We can then write¹⁵:

$$\frac{\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}} \leq 1 + \frac{2}{\ln(n)} + \frac{7}{\ln^2(n)} \approx 1.4277 \quad (8)$$

i.e.

$$\frac{\overline{\pi_2(n)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}} \leq \approx 1.885 \quad (9)$$

It is worth noting that the ratio $\frac{\overline{\pi_2(n)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}}$ has been studied by many authors (Weinstein, 2006) under the general condition: $\frac{\overline{\pi_2(n)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}} < 2C_2 + \varepsilon$. Recently, Wu (see [14]) proved that for sufficient large n : $\frac{\overline{\pi_2(n)}}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}} < \approx 4.5$

Part 2: $\pi_2(x)$ is upper bounded by $K \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}$ with $K \geq 1$

¹³i.e. $C(n_0)$.

¹⁴In fact the problem associated to divergence is that for a fixed ε , the error in a divergent series will reach to a ε -dependent minimum, but as more terms are added the error then increases without bound and tends to infinity.

¹⁵Even if the optimal truncation for $n \geq n_0$ should not be reached (i.e. more terms added), what changes would be only the value of the bound (which clearly increases).

Even if $\overline{\pi_2(n)}$ is numerically a very good estimation of $\pi_2(n)$ a little difference occurs, such that the ratio $\frac{\overline{\pi_2(n)}}{\pi_2(n)}$ by hypothesis tends to unity when n tends to infinity. If we look at the numerical figures up to 10^{18} we observe that the difference $\pi_2(n) - \overline{\pi_2(n)}$ changes sign many times. It is not clear whether the number of changes is finite or not because this would imply the solution of the still unproven twin prime conjecture.

Anyway, since by hypothesis

$$\pi_2(n) \sim 2C_2 \int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\int_2^n \frac{dx}{\ln^2(x)} \sim \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)} \quad (11)$$

we have:

$$\pi_2(n) \sim 2C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)} \quad (12)$$

Also in this case we have a convergent sequence

$$\{b_n\} = \frac{\pi_2(n)}{\frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}} \quad (13)$$

that is bounded *i.e.* for every $n \in N$ there is a real number $K \geq 1$ such that:

$$\pi_2(n) \leq K \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)} \quad (14)$$

Part 3: $\sum_{p,p+2 \text{ primes}} \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p+2}$ *is bounded by a convergent series*

Let us consider the sum:

$$\sum_{p,p+2 \text{ primes}} \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p+2} \quad (15)$$

Since $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p+2} \leq \frac{2}{p}$ the convergence of the series is equivalent to the convergence of $\sum_{p,p+2 \text{ primes}} \frac{1}{p}$, there are two possibilities: twin primes are finite in number (in this case the sum of the series is finite and the convergence is proved) or twin primes are not finite in number, in which case:

$$n = \pi_2(p_n) \leq K \frac{p_n}{\ln^2(p_n)} < K \frac{p_n}{\ln^2(n)} \text{ for every }^{16} n \in N$$

Hence:

$$\frac{1}{p_n} < K \frac{1}{n \ln^2(n)}, \quad \forall n \in N \quad (16)$$

¹⁶ $n = 1 \ p_1 = 3, n = 2 \ p_2 = 5, n = 3 \ p_3 = 11$ etc.

The study of convergence of the series $\sum_1^\infty \frac{1}{p_n}$ leads to:

$$\sum_1^\infty \frac{1}{p_n} = \frac{1}{3} + \sum_2^\infty \frac{1}{p_n} < \frac{1}{3} + K \sum_2^\infty \frac{1}{n \ln^2(n)} < +\infty \quad (17)$$

Results of section three

The HLC enables a simplified proof of the Brun's theorem (1921): the theorem represents a bridge between two undisputed milestones of Number Theory.

It is worth noting an historical detail: HLC and Brun's theorem are in a short distance of time but in spite of that, the possible correlation turned out not to be trivial: the convergence of the reciprocals of twin primes was indeed a great surprise for the whole scientific community.

4. From Hardy-Littlewood conjecture to Legendre's conjecture on twin primes

It is worth noting that an alternative expression of the prime number theorem (PNT) is $p_n \sim n \ln(n)$ and that Legendre's conjecture states there is a prime number p between n^2 and $(n+1)^2$ for every integer n . What was proved by Chen (see [5]) is that the number p can be either a prime or semiprime.

This part of the study, explores a similar statement concerning twin primes assuming that $\pi_2(n)$ is asymptotically equal to $2C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}$.

4.1 Conjecture framework

If $\pi_2(n) \sim 2C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2(n)}$ then $\ln(\pi_2(n)) \sim 2C_2 \ln(n) - 2C_2 \ln(\ln^2(n))$

but $\ln(\ln^2(n)) = o(\ln(n))$ hence $\ln(\pi_2(n)) \sim 2C_2 \ln(n)$

At the same time, by definition of the twin prime counting function $n = \pi_2(p_n) : p_n, p_{n+2} \in P$; then $\ln(n) = \ln(\pi_2(p_n))$ and we have $\ln(n) \sim 2C_2 \ln(p_n)$.

Since $n = \pi_2(p_n) \sim 2C_2 \frac{p_n}{\ln^2(p_n)}$ by hypothesis, we have:

$$n = \pi_2(p_n) \sim 2C_2 \frac{p_n}{\ln^2(p_n)} \sim \frac{p_n}{\ln^2(n)} \quad (18)$$

and in the end:

$$p_n \sim n \cdot \ln^2(n). \quad (19)$$

This suggests that the gap between consecutive twin primes: $p_n - p_{n-1} \sim \ln^2(n)$.

At the same time, since $((n+1)^3 - n^3) \sim 3n^2$ it follows that the size of the gap $[(n+1)^3, n^3]$ when $n \rightarrow +\infty$ will become larger than the largest gap between twin primes.

4.2 Iterative Method

While in the past (*e.g.* in the 1950s) papers used to report the findings up to $n = 10^6$ or little more, nowadays the standard is $n = 10^{18}$ even if no probabilistic or mathematical justification is provided, except for the increased computer power.

Starting from $n = 10^6$ the calculation has been carried out up to 10^{11} and is always verified. It is worth noting that as the value of n increases, it also increases the probability that the conjecture is true, since the twin prime gap becomes '*tendentially*' smaller than the gap $[n^3, (n+1)^3]$ (Table 6).

n	n^3	$(n+1)^3$	p	p+2
90	729000	753571	729269	729271
91	753571	778688	753587	753589
92	778688	804357	778697	778699
93	804357	830584	804521	804523
94	830584	857375	830741	830743
95	857375	884736	857567	857569
96	884736	912673	884789	884791
97	912673	941192	912797	912799
98	941192	970299	941207	941209
99	970299	1000000	970421	970423

Table 6: Output Example

4.3 Result of section four

If HLC is assumed, the still unproved Legendre’s conjecture can be extended to twin primes. Analytic justification and numerical findings up to 10^{11} allow to conjecture there is a twin prime between n^3 and $(n+1)^3$ for every integer n :

$$\exists (p_j, p_j + 2) : n^3 \leq p_j, p_j + 2 \leq (n + 1)^3 \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (20)$$

5 Connection between Legendre’s conjecture and Bertrand’s postulate in twin primes

In general terms, Bertrand’s postulate is a statement weaker than Legendre’s conjecture: it only guarantees with a pattern different from Legendre’s the existence of a prime number between n and $2n$. We will explore and prove the reverse implication in twin primes: starting from the statement of the extended Legendre’s conjecture (Eq.20) we can develop for twin primes a statement similar to Bertrand’s postulate:

$$\exists (p_n, p_n + 2) : m^2 < (p_n, p_n + 2) < 2m^2 \quad \forall m \geq 2, m \in \mathbb{N} \quad (21)$$

By the way, it’s worth noting that both eq. (20) and (21) imply the statement of the infamous Twin Prime Conjecture.

Proof

Let:

- $I_L = [n^3, (n+1)^3]$ be the extended Legendre’s conjecture interval in twin primes, range d_L ,
- $I_B = [m^2, 2m^2]$ be the extended Bertrand’s postulate interval in twin primes, range d_B .

We know, according to (20), that there exists a twin prime $(p_j, p_j + 2)$ such that:

$$n^3 < (p_j, p_j + 2) < (n + 1)^3 \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

The range d_B in extended Bertrand's postulate is $d_B = m^2$, while in Legendre's it is $d_L = 3n^2 + 3n + 1$. In order to compare d_B and d_L , let $m^2 = n^3$, i.e., $n = m^{2/3}$ with $n \in \mathbb{R}$. Involving floor and ceiling functions, we have:

$$n = \lfloor m^{2/3} \rfloor \quad \text{or} \quad n = \lceil m^{2/3} \rceil \quad \text{with } n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Hence,

$$d_L = 3\lfloor m^{2/3} \rfloor^2 + 3\lfloor m^{2/3} \rfloor + 1 \quad (22)$$

or

$$d_L = 3\lceil m^{2/3} \rceil^2 + 3\lceil m^{2/3} \rceil + 1 \quad (23)$$

while Bertrand's range is $d_B = m^2$.

Clearly, d_B becomes larger than d_L as m increases, but the two intervals I_L and I_B don't correspond. The simplest way to fix this problem is to notice that every Bertrand's interval d_B must include *at least* one Legendre's d_L (and consequently at least one twin prime), when $d_B \geq 2d_L$, regardless of whether we take into account eq. (22) or eq. (23).

Applying the floor function (eq. (22)), it's immediate to verify numerically that this happens when $m \geq 16$. At the same time, it's also easy to find a twin prime for $m = 2$ to $m = 15$, e.g., $I_B = [4, 8]$ (5,7), $I_B = [9, 18]$ (11,13), $I_B = [16, 32]$ (17,19), ..., $I_B = [225, 450]$ (227,229). Hence, it can be easily concluded that statement (21) holds for every $m \geq 2$.

The same procedure applied to prime numbers points out the reason why Bertrand's postulate doesn't imply Legendre's conjecture: in this case, we have $d_L = 2\sqrt{m} + 1$ vs. $d_B = m$, and clearly, Bertrand's interval grows larger than Legendre's, and to prove this implication, a few more hypotheses would be required.

6. Andrica's conjecture on twin primes

Let $m_j = p_j + 1$ (i.e., the middle point between twin primes) from Legendre's conjecture (Section 4.3) we have: $n^3 \leq m_j \leq (n + 1)^3$ and $(n + 1)^3 \leq m_{j+1} \leq (n + 2)^3$. So it comes naturally to conjecture:

$$\sqrt[n]{m_{j+1}} - \sqrt[n]{m_j} < 1, \quad \forall n \geq 3 \quad (24)$$

Eq.(24) has been verified up to 10^{12} .

Conclusions

Numerical and statistic findings even if not a proof, can provide some kind of indications and a large overview on many open problems and conjectures with amazing connections among them.

With this awareness that balances our thinking, the study has identified certain regularities in the pattern of twin primes in light of Dirichlet's theorem, while also revealing statistical randomness in how the reduced residue classes $(\text{mod } q)$ are filled.

Starting from the celebrated Hardy-Littlewood conjecture—whose error term has been analyzed to provide an analytic definition of the twin primes counting function—the study has also introduced an analytical proof of Brun's theorem without using sieve methods, along with an extension of the famous conjectures of Legendre, Bertrand, and Andrica to twin primes.

All of this allows us to take a deeper look into the world of twin primes and at the same time provides new future research directions.

Annex#1: Abbreviation list

HLC: first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture

BTh: Brun's theorem

LCj: Legendre's conjecture

Math: Mathematica software code

χ^2 : Chi Square Test

Quad-Core: Quad-core 2.67 GHz CPU

I7: I7 11th Gen. 2.80 GHz CPU

EL: Error Level

ITA: Innovative trend analysis

Q-Q plot: Quantile-Quantile plot

KPSS: Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin tests

FoD: First order difference analysis

SPt: Spearman correlation Test

PEt: Pearson correlation Test

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